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A METHODOLOGY FOR KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT STRATEGY DEVELOPMENT; MULTI-CASE STUDY IN THREE ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract

In order to evaluate and select the appropriate knowledge management strategy, a lot of organizational factors must be considered. On the other hand, in the approach of dynamic knowledge management strategy, the processes of creation and transferring of knowledge have direct effects on the selected strategies. The human-oriented and system-oriented approaches of knowledge management strategy are essentially different and need different infrastructures, methods and tools. In this research, the related literature about developing knowledge management strategy has been reviewed. The effective factors on knowledge management strategy have been extracted from different conceptual frameworks, models and methods. Then a comprehensive methodology for developing knowledge management strategy has been presented.

The factors of this methodology, which have direct effects on the final chosen strategy, include general business strategy, organizational structure, cultural factors and knowledge creation process in knowledge intensive area of the organization. Also in this methodology, the interrelated effect of information technology strategy and human resource strategy on the knowledge management strategy is considered and the final strategy is shown ranging from human oriented approach to system oriented approach.

The elements of this methodology have been validated in the form of the research hypothesis by asking the viewpoints of experts and all of them have been accepted. Three companies have used this methodology for developing.

Keyword(s): KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT, KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT STRATEGY, KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT STRATEGY MAKING, METHODOLOGY OF KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT STRATEGY